

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN DEVELOPING PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS USING VIRTUAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *In this article, the content of developing the pedagogical skills of future primary school teachers with the help of virtual technologies, the content and tasks of forming methodological possibilities of virtual education, the advantages and conveniences of virtual education. Aspects of using virtual education technology to increase the effectiveness of the educational process are considered.*

Keywords: *primary education, teacher, pedagogical skill, virtual educational technology, virtual educational environment, virtual educational environment, interactivity, virtual educational process control systems.*

In the educational system of our country, researches aimed at improving the educational system based on innovative technologies, strengthening its national soil, raising the training of socially active and qualified competitive personnel to the level of world requirements are being carried out on a large scale. Quality changes and high efficiency in the education system are directly related to their compatibility with world educational requirements and the extent to which the knowledge, skills and qualifications acquired by pedagogues are put into practice in their future work activities. Quality changes and high efficiency in education. As a result of introducing positive innovations in this field, quality and efficiency in education is ensured, and the process of pedagogical innovation is created [3].

Pedagogical education system is progressing, offering new, scientifically based models and technologies of modern education system to prepare future teachers for professional and innovative activities that meet the requirements of the time. The increasing status of the field of pedagogy in modern conditions and the increasing demand for qualified specialists in this direction determine the need to modernize their professional and pedagogical training in the integrated system of higher pedagogical education.

The process of improving the preparation of future teachers for pedagogical and innovative activities in higher education is based on the general rules of modernization of the continuous education system. The development of the idea of modernization of education and its reflection in modern scientific publications and normative documents means that it is necessary to understand its essence, the directions and ways of its implementation in higher education. Decision PQ-2909 of April 20, 2017 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further develop the higher education system" is a priority for the fundamental improvement of the higher education system, the socio-economic development of our country in accordance with the tasks, it was adopted in order to fundamentally revise the content of personnel training, to create the necessary conditions for the training of highly qualified specialists at the level of international standards [2]. Raising the field of pedagogy to a new level of quality requires restructuring the content and method of training quality specialists based on innovations. For this purpose, it is necessary to

improve the content and structural structure of the training system of future teachers in the field of pedagogy based on the requirements set by the state for this branch of education. The technology of improving the pedagogical practice of future specialists based on an innovative approach is one of the important tasks for higher education institutions.

Today, improving the educational system based on innovative technologies, strengthening its national ground, training socially active and qualified competitive personnel to the level of world standards is one of the urgent issues in the educational system of our country. Quality changes and high efficiency in the field of education depend on their compatibility with global educational requirements and the extent to which the competences acquired by pedagogues are put into practice in the future work activities. About this, in paragraph 7 of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 11, 2022 "On approval of the national program for the development of public education in 2022-2026" No. PF-134 and May 21, 2022 - in paragraph 2 of the PQ-289-Decision of June "On measures to improve the quality of pedagogical education and further development of higher educational institutions training pedagogic personnel", the 2-4th stage of higher educational institutions training pedagogic personnel in the form of full-time education the task of ensuring weekly training sessions for students in "4+2" order, including 4 days of classes in a higher educational institution, 2 days of practice in pre-school and general secondary educational institutions.

Development of human capital in our republic based on the requirements of the labor market, introduction of digital technologies and modern methods into the educational process, training of highly qualified, creative and systematic thinkers, able to make independent decisions based on international standards, demonstrating their intellectual abilities and moral integrity creation of necessary conditions for formation as a person is defined as the main strategic tasks. In-depth study of "Pedagogical skills" is important in finding a solution to this problem in higher pedagogical educational institutions. What is pedagogical skill? What is its essence? What do you need to know to get them? Modern pedagogy and psychology interpret the concept of "pedagogical skill" differently. For example, in the "Pedagogical Encyclopedia" the definition is explained as follows: "A skilled master of his profession, highly cultured, deeply knowledgeable of his subject, able to analyze the fields of related sciences well, perfect the methodology of education and training the specialist who has acquired it".

Possessing pedagogical skills, thoroughly mastering the secrets of pedagogical techniques, among all professions, the teaching profession acquires a special and important social importance. After all, a teacher is a memory of the soul of the young generation, a person who educates young people. Today, he trains the youth ideologically and politically, teaches them the laws of nature, society, social life, and development of thinking, prepares young people for work, helps them master the secrets of the profession, and helps them to understand socio-economic situations that are important for society. solves. This responsibility requires the teacher to be a skilled master of his profession, to have an educational impact on the students and to develop their interests, abilities, talents, beliefs and practical skills in every way. It requires a professional to find them. To do this, constantly improve the professional skills, skills and qualifications of teachers, take care of them in every way, create the necessary conditions, provide the necessary material, scientific-methodical and technical support, creative teachers' it is necessary to help to regularly increase initiative. Based on this, it is important to prepare skilled and responsible personnel who know their profession and specialty well.

The formation of pedagogical skills of students is primarily taught to teachers and educators in pedagogical creativity, pedagogical techniques, mutual cooperation between teachers and students in the educational process, communication tactics, speech culture, thinking, spiritual knowledge of the educator. organization and implementation of educational and educational work, in this process it teaches the characteristics of being able to control behavior and emotions. Provides information about the system of pedagogical activities that develop their profession. Pedagogical activity is the labor activity of specially trained teachers who are accountable to the society and the state in order to prepare the young generation for life and work. The system of abilities necessary for effective pedagogical activity of teachers: knowledge, ability to understand the child, observation, speech skills, organization, ability to see the future, distribution of attention, correct assessment of the situation, emergence timely elimination of all possible conflicts, making students interested in learning.

Students live in a "special" field of knowledge created by new communication tools that is much richer and more complex than any traditional method of education. With the emergence of informational priorities, virtual education can gradually return to self-education. The introduction of multimedia educational products is carried out not only by educational institutions, therefore, the educational process can be carried out directly outside the social institution, but "with a computer" individually.

Virtual education is closely related to distance education, but is not limited to it. It can (and does) occur in the normal face-to-face interactions of teachers, students, and subjects. Distance education technologies make it possible to expand the possibilities of daytime education by increasing the possibility of mutual use of students, teachers, specialists and information complexes located far from each other. The main goal of virtual education, as well as human education in general, is to determine and achieve one's destiny in the real world, including the virtual component.

Virtual education includes not only distance telecommunication education, but also "the process and result of the interaction of educational subjects and objects, along with their creation, the uniqueness of these objects and subjects clearly defined by

The virtual educational field is a space where the student can explore his external spheres through the activity of the student, who extends to the outside world and uses his emotional, intellectual and intellectual abilities.

- It includes the information content and communicative capabilities of local, corporate and global computer networks organized and used for educational purposes by all participants of the educational process;

- Created and developed for effective communication of all participants of the educational process;

In contrast to traditional methods of education, the nature of education is communication, which is indirect, both distant and traditionally "face-to-face". The virtual learning environment combines a rapidly growing, multi-level and multi-functional system:

1) innovative and traditional technologies specific to the interaction of participants in the educational process within the open model of asynchronous individual education;

2) information resources: databases and information, libraries, electronic educational materials, etc.;

3) modern software: software cabins, electronic communication.

Advantages of a virtual learning environment: Learner flexibility is illustrated by:

- Everything is placed in a convenient place because the trainer is implemented through Internet technologies;
- The distance from placement of students to educational institutions is not an obstacle for an effective educational process;
- They participate at a convenient time for themselves. Each person has his own biological "clock" and can choose and change the time of classes according to them;
- By building his own didactics, he revises the theoretical and practical training processes, can refer to the saved materials from previous lessons and communicate with the teacher through the virtual space;
- Concentrate on specific sections, block each section, module and time required. So, you can save time by doing it faster;
- The costs of the student and the educational system for the implementation of educational activities will be reduced in order to effectively use the educational field, time and technical resources.

In conclusion, we can say that the pedagogical education system is developing, offering new, scientifically based models and technologies of the modern education system to prepare future teachers for professional and innovative activities that meet the requirements of the time. The increasing status of the field of pedagogy in modern conditions and the increasing demand for qualified specialists in this field determine the need to modernize their professional and pedagogical training in the integrated system of higher pedagogical education. The process of improving the preparation of future teachers for pedagogical and innovative activities in higher education is based on the general rules of modernization of the continuous education system.

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